

THE IMPACT OF EMPLOYING TELEGRAM IN LEARNING

Yulduz Qurbonova Umarovna
Mehridin Yahyoyev Sabriddinovich

Bukhara State Pedagogical Institution Foreign Languages Department Bukhara,
Uzbekistan

qurbonovayulduz98@gmail.com

Annotation: XXI century is a period of innovations and, similarly, in teaching we apply different techniques and tools. Most of them are available for online usage since it is a more convenient way for the young learners. The article below discusses about one of the most widely used android apps, Telegram, additionally, you may gain knowledge about various scientists' opinions about the issue. Furthermore, possible ways to use the program are given in order to make this article more useful for the readers

Key words: telegram, impact, curriculum, experiment, participants, educational, learners. reliability, research, validity, female

The article "The Impact of Employing Telegram App on Iranian EFL Beginners' Vocabulary Teaching and Learning" by the authors Hossein Heidari Tabrizi and Nareges Onvani, is aimed at researching how Telegram, as the source of networking through a social media, can affect the learners. The investigation has been applied for Iranian students who are about 10-14 years old and who are beginners in English language. The process continued for 8 weeks: for four weeks teacher conducted the lesson through Telegram and in the next four weeks students experienced traditional classes. The importance of this research, as the author states, so far there have been so many challenges in language learning and one of them was the deficiency of creativity and focusing on the same curriculum. However, Telegram opened a way for the learners to be autonomous learners by self-studying, finding out what they really need and do not. To research questions have been mentioned in the article that are about the effect of Telegram on teaching vocabulary for Iranian EFL beginners and the other, what attitude the learners will have: positive or negative. As the participants of the study 31 female student from the English Language Institute in Iran were selected whose age varied from 10 to 14. They were all Persian speakers with the same cultural and educational background. For the research various instruments have been chosen, such as pretest, posttest and attitude questionnaire as

an addition to Placement Interchange Test that aimed at identifying whether all the participants have the same level of language proficiency. Making sure that the participants are homogenous in a language, pretest was conducted in order to know whether the words given were new for the learners or not. After these investigations proved the reliability of the research, four-week-online and four-week-traditional classes were organized. Finally, in order to know how effective was the process, the same questionnaire that were used in pretest stage with 40 multiple choice questions, were distributed for the learners. The level of questions was appropriate for the level of learners and they were easy to understand, however, there were instructors to monitor and to help when necessary. After applying Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests, it was revealed that Telegram-based classes were significantly effective in teaching vocabulary, which can be seen by the percentages that: classes through Telegram app showed 3.89, while traditional classes were 3.00 percent high. Each time reliability and validity of the tests were checked to provide a concrete result after all. The findings showed that Telegram-based approach has a higher score that traditionally taught classes and they can be effective in vocabulary teaching classes for Iranian beginner female learners.

In my perspective, the theme is really crucial for English language teachers in a current time, since Telegram is being included in each and every person's daily life. So many people, especially, young generation spare their lots of time to social networks, such as You Tube, What's Up, Telegram and Facebook since they suggest multi-functional colorful media sources that are new for the users. As a proof, I would like to cite Van der Beemt, et all (2010) that they confirm younger people spend a considerable portion of their daily life for social medias for interaction. Chalak (2017), Kabilan (2010) and Girgin (2011) considered that Facebook, Telegram and Tweeter and some other social networks help the users to experience English language in different situations, in addition, Telegram provides "private, friendly, fun, simple and interesting interaction" between teachers and students. Based on these facts it can be said that Telegram-based classes generates a positive attitude in the participants, surely, discovering news for each time gives more and more self-content, desire and motivation. As professors Mashahdi Heidar and Kaviani (2016) described, Telegram owns a unique technological and pedagogical priorities for the learners. However, on the other hand, some students who had less knowledge on using Telegram and technology, had a problem in the process and they felt anxious about their results and did not believe in the effectiveness of e-learning. It should be admitted that not all of the youth, or adults, can use up-to-date

technologies and apps with prevents their freedom and self-beliefs. What I want to say is that, whenever a teacher wants to apply this type of method, pre-instructions should be given in order to avoid this kind of unpleasant situations.

Giving a rise to conclusion, I would like to say that this article has been useful for me. I read the article with an interest focusing on details because it is about one of the most important topics in language teaching. Applying technology and online sources in the class is the demand of the current period in teaching not only a language, but also the other courses. The quote by Arthur W. Chickering and Stephen C. Ehrmann, grabbed my attention and I was really impressed by that “Students do not learn much just sitting in classes listening to teachers, memorizing prepackaged assignments and spitting out answers. They must talk about what they are learning, write reflectively about it, relate it to past experiences and apply it to their daily lives”. I assume, it tells what needs to be mentioned about online classes through apps and applying technology into classes. However, most importantly, designing a lesson and how to use these sources demand much effort and experience from the teacher as well.

References:

1. Chalak. A. (2017). Linguistic features of English textese and digitalk of Iranian EFL Students. Paper presented in the Fourth International Conference on Language, Discourse and Pragmatics (LDP, 2017), 25-27 January, 2017, Ahvaz, Iran.
2. Girgin, E. G. (2011). A web 2.0 tool for language teaching with flash content, *Procedia Computer Science*, 3, 627–631.
3. Kabilan, M. K. (2010). Facebook: An online environment for learning of English in institutions of higher education? *Internet and Higher Education*, 13(4), 179-187.
4. Mashhadi Heidar, D. & kaviani, M. (2016). The social impact of telegram as a social network on teaching English vocabulary among Iranian intermediate EFL learners. *Sociological Studies of Youth* 23, 65-76.
5. Van der Beemt, A. A. J., Akkerman, S. F. & Simons, P.R.J. (2010). Pathways in interactive media practices among young people. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 35(4), 419-434.
6. Qurbonova Y.U. (2024), Pragmatics and Awareness Raising Tasks in Language Learning <https://multijournals.org/index.php/excellencia-imje/article/view/606/663vvv>